

Dyes derived from Thiohydantoin. Part II.

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In Part I of this series (Pendse and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 963) thiohydantoin was condensed with a number of nitroso- and isonitroso-compounds resulting in products possessing interesting dyeing properties. It has now been condensed with a series of aromatic aldehydes. Condensations of thiohydantoin with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde vanillin and piperonal seem to have been carried out (*cf.* Johnson, Wheeler and Nicolet, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 1973; Johnson and Bengis, *ibid*, 1913, 35, 1609; Ruhemann and Stapleton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 246). But whereas, the previous authors used glacial acetic acid and fused sodium acetate as the condensing agent, we used acetic anhydride, which brought about the condensations much more easily, but the products obtained were found to be acetyl derivatives of the condensation products, which can have three alternative constitutions. For example, the condensation product of benzaldehyde and thiohydantoin can have one of the first three alternative structures given below:—

Structure (I) is very unlikely, because in this form the acetyl group would be very unstable, since it has been found that 3-acetylthiohydantoin and 3-benzoylthiohydantoin on condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of glacial acetic acid and fused sodium

acetate, very readily suffers splitting off of the acidyl groups with formation of benzylidenethiohydantoin. Hence position 3 from which an acid group is so easily split off is very unlikely to be the place in which an acidyl group can be subsequently introduced. Then only remains structures (II) and (III) between which the latter seems to be the most likely, because from the point of view of a theory of colour advanced by one of us (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3, 99) this structure which contains a carbon-nitrogen double bond, would be more coloured than benzylidenethiohydantoin (V) which contains a carbon-oxygen double bond whereas structure (II) would have practically the same colour as benzylidenethiohydantoin, since it contains the same type of linkage. During the course of these investigations it was found that the acetyl derivatives of the condensation products are always more coloured than the deacetylated compounds which are readily obtained by hydrolysis of the former with alkali. Hence structure (III) is the most probable configuration for the condensation products.

It was also observed that the condensation products are very easily hydrolysed by alkali and thereby revert from the acetylated enolic (III) to the free keto-type (V) via the intermediate unstable free enolic form (IV). However, in some instances the complete reversion took some time, whereas in some cases a fair amount of heat had to be applied during the process of crystallisation or the subsequent drying. Thus acetylbenzylidenethiohydantoin on dissolving in 20% sodium hydroxide solution rapidly undergoes hydrolysis, and the clear solution on the addition of dilute acids throws down a bright yellow precipitate, which on crystallisation from alcohol and subsequent drying in vacuum, melts at 220° on the second day, at 232-34° on the 6th day, at 242-45° on the 12th day, at 255-58° on the 18th day, 259° on the 24th day, after which the melting point remains constant. However the yellow precipitate on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid or amyl alcohol and subsequent drying in the air oven at 120°, gives a product melting at 259° in one day. In order to remove any doubt that the lower melting products might not be impure specimens of the higher melting product, all the different samples were analysed and the analytical results were found to be practically identical. From these it was concluded that the lowest melting point was that of the pure enolic compound, the intermediate values

were those of various mixtures of enol and keto types and the highest melting point was that of pure keto compound. In order to avoid a complexity of melting points, all the compounds described in this paper were prepared for a second time, twice recrystallised from glacial acetic acid and dried at 120° before the melting points were determined and recorded.

The following aromatic aldehydes have been condensed with thiohydantoin in presence of acetic anhydride and the condensation products isolated both in the acetylated enolic and free keto-forms:— benzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, *m*- and *p*-amino-benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, β -resorcyraldehyde, vanillin, piperonal, cinnamaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. The condensation product of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde has been obtained in the form of a quinoline derivative (VI).

The same product is obtained when *o*-nitrobenzylidenethiohydantoin is reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid.

Most of the compounds described in this paper are highly coloured substances which dye wool and silk in fine shades of yellow and orange from an acid bath. They also dye cotton direct from alkaline bath containing sodium carbonate to shades which are only slightly weaker than those on wool and silk. Solutions of these substances in alkali on standing are apt to decompose due to oxidation and hydrolysis, and in strongly acid solution the thiohydantoin ring is ruptured giving phenylalanine and substitution products. The absorption maxima of these dyes have also been determined and they are given in the tables at the end of the paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiohydantoin, prepared according to the method given in *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 137, was condensed with aromatic aldehydes as follows: equimolecular proportions of the aldehydes and thiohydantoin were

heated together under reflux with 3-5 times the weight of acetic anhydride for periods varying from $\frac{1}{2}$ to 3 hours. The solution was then poured into water, whereby the acetylated condensation product was precipitated in flocks which were collected, washed, dried and crystallised from various solvents, mostly from pyridine and glacial acetic acid, in glistening needles. Generally speaking these substances are sparingly soluble in most of the ordinary solvents and have got a remarkable power of crystallisation.

The deacetylation was effected by warming the above compounds with 20% solution of sodium hydroxide until completely dissolved and then precipitating the cooled solution with dilute hydrochloric acid. Then resulting products were then crystallised from glacial acetic acid or amyl alcohol in the form of silky needles which were dried at 120°. These deacetylated products are more soluble than the corresponding acetylated compounds in the ordinary organic solvents, and they have remarkable dyeing power for wool, silk and cotton. In caustic alkalis they are freely soluble. For the sake of abbreviation, the properties of all these compounds are given in tabular form at the end of the paper.

TABLE I.

Acetylated Compounds.

Name. (A = acetyl, T = thiohydantoin).	Appearance.	M. p.	Absorption maxima in glacial acetic acid (wave-lengths).	P. c. of sulphur (theoretical values in brackets.)
A-benzylidene-T.	Pale yellow needles	260°	4540	13.0 (13.0)
A-o-nitrobenzylidene-T.	Orange "	241°	5060	11.7 (11.5)
A-m-nitrobenzylidene-T.	Lemon-yellow "	263°	4930	11.2 (11.5)
A-p-nitrobenzylidene-T.	" "	270°	4950	11.7 (11.5)
Di-A-o-hydroxybenzylidene-T.	Deep yellow "	237°	4820	11.0 (10.5)
Di-A-m-hydroxybenzylidene-T.	" "	250°	4710	10.9 (10.5)
Di-A-p-hydroxybenzylidene-T.	" "	265°	4810	10.8 (10.5)
2 : 3-Thiocarbamidoquinoline-T.	Pale yellow prisms.	213°	—	15.6 (15.9)
Di-A-m-aminobenzylidene-T.	" needles.	Above 285°	4710	10.7 (10.5)
Di-A-p-aminobenzylidene-T.	" "	" "	4750	10.9 (10.5)
Tri-A-3 : 5-dihydroxybenzylidene-T.	Orange yellow "	240°	4880	8.6 (8.8)
A-p-methoxybenzylidene-T.	Brownish-yellow needles.	265°	4720	11.4 (11.59)
A-3 : 4-methylenedioxybenzylidene-T.	" "	275°	4790	11.6 (11.1)
Di-A-vanillidene-T.	Yellow needles.	261°	4800	9.9 (9.5)
A-cinnamylidene-T.	Deep yellow "	267°	4820	12.3 (11.8)
A-p-dimethylaminobenzylidene-T.	Bright red "	272°	5110	11.6 (11.1)

TABLE II.
Deacetylated Compounds.

Name. (T = thiobhydantoin).	Appearance.	M. p.	Shade on wool and silk.	Absorption maxima in alcohol (wave- length.).	P. c. of sulphur (theoretical values in brackets.).
Benzylidene-T.	Pale yellow needles.	259°	Lemon yellow	4450	15.2 (15.5)
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-T.	Orange yellow "	249°	Orange	4960	13.0 (12.85)
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-T.	Pale yellow "	257°	Bright yellow	4860	13.1 (12.85)
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-T.	" "	266°	" "	4910	13.2 (12.85)
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzylidene-T.	" "	231°	" "	4740	13.9 (14.5)
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzylidene-T.	" "	256°	" "	4680	14.5 (14.5)
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzylidene-T.	" "	270°	" "	4730	14.1 (14.5)
<i>m</i> -Aminobenzylidene-T.	" "	Above 285°	" "	4670	14.3 (14.5)
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzylidene-T.	" "	" "	" "	4710	14.2 (14.5)
3:5-Dihydroxybenzylidene-T.	Bright yellow "	210°	Brownish-yellow	4760	13.9 (13.6)
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzylidene-T.	" "	255°	Canary "	4680	13.6 (13.65)
3:4-Methylenedioxybenzylidene-T.	" "	283°	Deep "	4740	12.9 (12.9)
Vanillidene-T.	" "	240°	" "	4750	13.9 (13.8)
Cinnamylidene-T.	" "	260°	" "	4760	13.5 (13.9)
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzylidene-T.	Light red "	252°	Orange-red	4980	12.4 (12.9)

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